

Why experts believe citizen scientists need training

The CS Track research team, led by partners Christine Urban and Michael Strähle from the Wissenschaftsladen Wien - Science Shop Vienna, has published a report called [Conceptual Framework for Analytics Tools](#), which builds on the preceding report [Framework Conceptual Model](#) and lays the conceptual foundation for the project. This document maps citizen science landscapes in the European Union and beyond, funding programmes, policies, advocacy and working groups, and opportunities for participating in citizen science activities. Moreover, the report presents an overview of educational citizen science activities in schools that complements the previously published literature review on citizen science activities in education. This document also includes interviews with African, Asian, European and American experts on Open Science, research ethics and research integrity to supplement the literature review included in the preceding report.

In total 12 experts were interviewed, 7 Open Science specialists and 5 experts on research ethics and integrity. Since citizen science is part of Open Science and not every country has a specific citizen science policy, the expert interviews focused on Open Science in general and citizen science. While citizen science offers great potential to enrich the scientific landscape and community, experts stress that it is important to understand what can be achieved with Open Science practices and what not and to manage expectations.

For instance, Rebecca Lave (Indiana University Bloomington, USA) pointed out that scientists might miss out on something by partially outsourcing data collection to volunteers. For perhaps scientists would notice something in data collection that citizens would not. The opportunities for unplanned fortunate discoveries might be reduced.

Read the full report to learn more about citizen science benefits, ethical challenges and discover several suggestions as to how different issues can be mitigated.

Download the full report [here](#).

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